

Tradition Verses Modernity in Salman Rushdie's *Fury*

N. Moorthy

Ph.D Part Time Research Scholar

Assistant Professor of English, GTN Arts College, Dindugul

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Abstract

This article comprises of woman's firm growth and feminism in Indian Fiction in English. Commencement from conventional phase, travelling to transitional stage and finally accomplishing modernity is studied critically with suggestions from the novels by Salman Rushdie. Female characters seek for their goals in the normal tasks of womanhood and in helping her family members. She often does not locate what she struggles for. The earliest consciousness of a woman, charged with misery and response and it looks as if to be in her to have brimmed and over-flowed, and expressed the need for liberation.

Keywords: self-assured, assertive, educated, protesting, ambitious, identity.

Rushdie's female protagonists fight endless battles to continue in the society where they are still slaves to habits, parents, husbands, and children. It is remarkable that the novelist expresses his deep anxiety about the problems, being faced by a woman in male-dominated society. He treats mainly with the troubles, faced by the Indian women. His learned protagonists try to state their personality and make an effort to lead a moderate life. Firmly, Rushdie pressures on the changing images of woman, from traditional into modern gradually more.

Rushdie's works encourage the readers understanding of the psyche of a woman, who is caught in the web of relationships, partly made by her, and partly made for her. The women's inner struggle between the desire to take care of their husbands and children and the desire to discover deeper modes of fulfilment that falls outside the traditional social norms. In these novels the reader notices the traditionally glorified woman reinstated with the genuine modern one, who is trying to throw off the burden, she has been carrying for ages. The image of woman is changing with the passage of time. The protagonists, portrayed by this novelist, are away from the traditional portrayals of the self-sacrificing, enduring, meek and quiet woman. They are the modern portrayals of self-assured, assertive, educated, protesting and ambitious ones; making society aware of their needs and proving their identities.

Rushdie portrays the changing image of women moving away from traditional depiction of lasting, self-sacrificing women into self-confident assertive and motivated women making society know of

their needs and in this way provided that a medium for self expression. He has been triumphant in creating brawny women protagonists who reject to get compressed under the burden of their personal tragedies, and face life with great guts and power. Fury draws upon the Roman myth of the three furies: Tisiphone, Alecto and Megaera, the female embodiments of vengeance.

Rushdie's novels show a marked slant to the beautiful, in the woman, and the plain, almost ugly in the man. The reader is introduced to Mila and Neela and Eleanor and every time, Rushdie takes care in introducing them as women in ire physical sense.

Solanka and Mila both play act their fantasies while continuing a charade of innocence, "In that charmed space, during Mila's visits, almost complete silence remained the norm. There were murmurs and whispers but no more" (F 136). Dr. Jann Gumbiner, a psychologist and a daughter of a divorced mother, shares her own experience in her article *Divorce Hurts Children, Even Grown Ones* as:

During the 70s, when the psychological literature first discussed the effects of divorce on children, the general view was that divorce doesn't have to harm children. But, it does. My grades went down. Not studying was a form of rebellion, anger, and apathy. I really didn't care what became of me. Perhaps, the kid is stuck with a depressed mother who can't leave her room, clean up the kitchen, or take the child to school. This child is ashamed to invite friends home from school and friendships suffer. My brother couldn't play Little League because there was no one to drive him to games. Extra-curricular activities suffer. (Gumbiner 1)

Jack Rhinehart, the phone-smasher invited Solanka to watch the Holland-Yugoslavia Euro 2000 Football quarter final on pay-per-view. After watching, Solanka has refreshed in Rhinehart's building. When he climbs out of the cab at Rhinehart's building, he sees a woman who is in shades rushing into it; jostling him later he remembers that she is familiar to him. Her name is Monica, Rhinehart has tried to get divorce for years, but his wife denies to give him. Solanka has wondered how a man with so much energy would handle a woman in a inferior manner. Rhinehart has done his wife wrong which cannot be denied. But he doesn't speak of the slow deep pain of a child. Instead of divorcing him she has told him sweetly that, she intends to make the rest of his life a misery, bleed him slowly.

Rushdie goes on to bring out the differences between Neela and Mila and one can instantly see that both are different types of Fury. Neela is the quiet, seething anger that is not quick to flare up but lethal when it does and Mila is the spontaneous bubbling over turbid anger that is deadly but does not last long. This duration can even be compared to the time they have in Professor Solanka's life. Mila is an obsession, but also a weakness, but Neela is a calming presence that means more.

Rushdie considers it a triumph of sorts when this woman who has everything going for her, is attracted to a man who is unremarkable. He also seems to indicate that these women seek out the wrong kind of man for themselves: "Sensing in him ferocity of commitment that was rarely found in modern men, women had allowed themselves these wised up cautious women" (F 29-30). And once they have these men, the women find nothing strange in subsuming their own identities in order to keep them. "To hold on to her beautiful Eddie, the college sports hero- whom she described to Solanka as "not the brightest bulb, but a dear heart and to whom a brainy, cultured woman would not doubt be a threat and a turnoff- she had dimmed her own light" (F 116).

Neela works as a producer. She is specialized in documentary programming for television. She is planning a project that could take her back to her roots. Professor Solanka sees the hot blood rising in her to the conflict of Ethnic 'Elbee' community. Neela herself is determined to march. But this conflict is not a small matter for the beautiful Neela, she is still connected to her origins and Solanka almost envies her for it. When Solanka has stepped out of the house, he sees a headline; concrete killer strikes again. Below that headline "Who was the Man in the Panama Hat?"

is written in smaller type. Everything has changed at once, darkness rushes in through the open window, blinding him.

Some years back Solanka has gone for vacation at the cottage in the ‘springs with Rhinehart and his’ waitress of the moment, who is a dead ringer for the cartoon sexpot Betty Boop and to whom Rhinehart refers affectionately as Roscoe. He has drunk in the men-only drinking session, and drives home. Professor Malik Solanka speaks to his mirthful friend of the abnegation of the self he couldn’t say that at he is a knife in the dark and he endangers those he loves.

Saskia “sky” schuyler today’s big picture, and her predecessors have their own power of smiles. They are not poor girls, but they are penniless now, she is a great girl, a living doll, but she is very perfect in business. She sees business as a business. Her mother is handling it all. This woman is made of iron and she never sheds a tear. She is only nineteen but she is a dedicated fashionist, a linguist and pianist. She is also an expert horse woman, an archer with hopes of making the Sydney Olympic team, a long-distance swimmer, a fabulous dancer, a great cook, a happy weak end painter a hoster in her mother’s grand manner, sensual in newspaper. Her friends are Bindy Candell and Ren Klein.

These three young women are born to be trophies but unfortunately they are killed by concrete killers. These dead girls are conformed to Eleanor’s definition of Desdemona’s. Othello has broken them simply to reveal their lack of humanity, their breakability. They are the android women dolls of the modern age, mechanized, computerized but fully realized avatars of human beings. These dolls have tales to tell. Behind their mechanism, they are stuffed with behavioural chips, thoroughly programmed for action, so perfectly groomed and war drooped, that there is no room left in them for messy humanity. Thus the three have represented the final step in the transformation of the cultural history of the doll. They are more free than any women in any country in anytime, and they belong to no man, whether father or lover or boss. They are nobody’s dolls, but their own women, playing with their own appearance, their own sexuality, and their own stories: the first generation of young women to be truly in control. They can be businesswomen and flirts, profound and superficial, serious and light and they could make those decisions for themselves. They have all that are emancipation, sex appeal, cash and they too love them. No one can take them away from these girls. Such girls are killed by the concrete killer, Solanka tears burying his head into his hands.

Saskiaschuyler lives in an apartment but she doesn’t like this ugly building. She hates the apartment, her parent’s former Manhattan pied-a-Terre, “If she wins, she’ll be off to D.C and the senate, and if she loses, she’ll leave even faster” (F 97). She plans to sell this Madison. Then she walks out by herself and she never comes back. Her body has found near the Midtown Tunnel. A study of the last hours of Lauren Klein and Bindy Candell shows that they too come house late, refuse their boyfriends. As if these girls have turned Life away then set out to keep their assignations with Death. They have not been robbed nor have they mentioned seeing the Panama-hated stranger “lurking oddly”. “It’s like somebody sentenced her to death and carried out that sentence in, like, cold blood”. (F 97).

Though the women, she pictures, are intelligent, smart and resourceful, they are deprived of freedom and they lack guts to openly defy the social order and are torn between traditional norms and modern attitudes. To recollect the words of Walker Percy quoted in his book “Lost in the Cosmos: The Last Self-Help Book”:

Marriage and family life are disappointing. Even among defenders of traditional family values, e.g., Christians and Jews, certain dreariness must be inferred, if only from the average time of TV viewing. Dreary as TV is, it is evidently not as dreary as Mom talking to Dad or the kids talking to either. (Percy 27).

Neela demonstrates that in affairs of the heart she is very much like the man and what women had always accused him of being. When she loved Solanka, she loved one hundred percent, with no holds barred; but plainly she is also an axe-murder capable at any moment of severing the head of a suddenly rejected love, and she has told him, with great seriousness “that you are the last man with whom I will ever sleep”. (F 230) The power of such promises is great, and under their enchantment he has even allowed himself to dream of return, has permitted himself to believe that the past could be had been stripped of its power, so that in the future all things could be achieved. But now Neela has vanished like a conjurer’s assistant and his strength too has gone with her. Without her he could never walk the Indian Streets again. If she forgives him, he would be the servant of all her desires. He begins to speak with greater animation and looked directly at Neela. Neela has gone she did not come back. Young men and women have attended Solanka’s daily needs. The women characters in the novels of Salman Rushdie eminent radiance from within and without and use beauty as a mean to an end, rather than allow themselves to be defined in purely corporeal terms.

The women characters struggle for their individuality and fight with family and society through which they drive into a committed attempt to shape individuality for themselves as capable women of with flawless surroundings. Rushdie has depicted her protagonists as women caught in the clash between the fervours of the flesh and the yearning to be a part of the political and intellectual movements of the day. He declares that writing in India tends to involve the family and community to a far greater extent than in the West. Here, women are commonly defined in terms of their roles.

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